

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

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Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	186	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	84.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	8.97	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	469	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.67	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
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	Matrix: Water

Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.387	mg/L	10	0.005	(0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01	(0.1)	2/10/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.137	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	0.0160	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.57	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.51	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0061	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	636	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.73	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.59	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	659	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	218	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	266	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.19	meq/L	1		
Cations total	37.16	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.33	%	1		
SiO2	20.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2220	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-01	Customer sample ID: GS-1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	814	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	184	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	83.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.00	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	456	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.387	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020

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Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.136	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.72	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0135	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.70	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.60	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	658	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	223	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	267	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.24	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.39	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.21	%	1		
SiO2	20.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2200	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-02	Customer sample ID: GS-2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	803	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
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Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	182	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	82.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	8.69	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	455	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.56	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.143	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.13	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0145	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.68	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.90	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	224	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	268	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.06	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.13	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.10	%	1		
SiO2	19.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-03	Customer sample ID: GS-3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	793	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	183	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	81.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	8.86	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	443	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.48	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020

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Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.141	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.23	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0149	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	648	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.52	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.68	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	678	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	225	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	270	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	37.04	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.62	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.96	%	1		
SiO2	19.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2220	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-04	Customer sample ID: GS-4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	793	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3210	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		2/7/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	187	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	84.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	8.91	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	465	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.65	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.133	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.16	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0136	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.62	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.90	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	654	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	225	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	275	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/7/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.09	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.97	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.22	%	1		
SiO2	19.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2210	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-05	Customer sample ID: GS-5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	812	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		2/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	181	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	81.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	19.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	8.69	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	444	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.375	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.135	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Silicon	9.24	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0051	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0144	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Chloride	633	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.59	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrate	0.80	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/24/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	227	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	274	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.20	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.51	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.97	%	1		
SiO2	19.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2180	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-06	Customer sample ID: GS-6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	787	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1610	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	92.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	34.4	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	12.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.4	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	225	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.66	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0027	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.042	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.191	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0034	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.080	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.015	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.6	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Strontium	1.65	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0030	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0034	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Chloride	210	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/24/2020
Sulfate	274	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	274	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	324	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	5	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.20	meq/L	1		
Cations total	17.55	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.00	%	1		
SiO2	27.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1050	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-07	Customer sample ID: SS-1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	373	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1600	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	96.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	34.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	12.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	11.8	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	224	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.67	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Barium	0.043	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/10/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Boron 11	0.190	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/10/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Copper 65	0.0043	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Lithium	0.067	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.3	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/10/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.62	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/10/2020
Uranium	0.0033	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020
Zinc 66	0.0033	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.11	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Chloride	208	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.50	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/24/2020
Sulfate	269	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	277	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	327	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	6	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.10	meq/L	1		
Cations total	17.65	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.59	%	1		
SiO2	26.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1040	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-08	Customer sample ID: SS-2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	380	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1630	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	98.1	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	34.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	12.7	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.1	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	226	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.70	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0028	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.043	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.191	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0056	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.075	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.4	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Strontium	1.65	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0029	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0187	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.12	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Chloride	212	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.50	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/24/2020
Sulfate	270	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	280	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	327	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	7	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.29	meq/L	1		
Cations total	17.88	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.68	%	1		
SiO2	26.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1050	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-09	Customer sample ID: SS-3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	387	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1620	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	98.5	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	34.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	12.4	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	221	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.67	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.042	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.187	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0049	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.077	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.2	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Strontium	1.66	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0029	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0060	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Chloride	218	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020
Fluoride	1.46	mg/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/24/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/24/2020
Sulfate	277	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	281	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	330	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	6	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.61	meq/L	1		
Cations total	17.69	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.22	%	1		
SiO2	26.1	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1060	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-10	Customer sample ID: SS-4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	388	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1260	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	101	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	35.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	12.7	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	228	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.72	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.042	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.192	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0048	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.077	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.1	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Strontium	1.69	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0032	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0078	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Chloride	221	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.49	mg/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/25/2020
Sulfate	279	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	284	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	333	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	6	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.81	meq/L	1		
Cations total	18.20	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.07	%	1		
SiO2	25.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1080	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-11	Customer sample ID: SS-5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	399	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1680	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.6	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	103	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	35.6	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Potassium	13.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.2	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/10/2020
Sodium	232	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	2/10/2020
Strontium	1.76	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.043	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.198	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0060	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.081	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.5	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Strontium	1.74	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0031	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0045	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Chloride	225	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.48	mg/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	2/25/2020
Sulfate	283	mg/L	5	1 (5)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	283	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	330	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	7	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	17.98	meq/L	1		
Cations total	18.47	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.34	%	1		
SiO2	26.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	1090	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-12	Customer sample ID: SS-6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	403	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3980	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	239	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	88.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	23.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	11.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	581	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.30	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.016	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.482	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0078	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.189	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	12.4	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.08	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0117	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0069	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.60	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	795	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.87	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	1.12	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	820	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	274	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	334	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	45.09	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.10	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.02	%	1		
SiO2	26.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2750	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-13	Customer sample ID: ESS-1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	963	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4010	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	240	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	88.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	23.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	586	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.34	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0116	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.473	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.195	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	13.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.15	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0116	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	0.0062	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.77	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	799	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.97	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	1.91	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	821	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	275	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	336	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	45.32	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.32	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.00	%	1		
SiO2	28.2	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2760	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-14	Customer sample ID: ESS-2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	963	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4060	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		2/28/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	246	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	88.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	23.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	13.9	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	575	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.28	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.016	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.471	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0097	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.194	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	13.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.24	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0124	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	0.0061	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0129	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.55	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	803	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.97	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	1.40	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	829	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	275	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	336	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	2/28/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	45.59	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.18	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.45	%	1		
SiO2	29.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2770	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-15	Customer sample ID: ESS-3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	979	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4090	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	248	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	89.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	25.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	15.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	585	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.39	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.016	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.478	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.190	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	15.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.28	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0117	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.53	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	807	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.91	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	825	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	324	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	395	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.56	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.79	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.83	%	1		
SiO2	33.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2820	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-16	Customer sample ID: ESS-4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	986	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4050	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	246	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	90.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	23.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	591	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.39	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.470	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	0.0081	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.188	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	13.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.17	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0122	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	0.0056	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	0.0088	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.68	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	813	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.98	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	1.44	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	845	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	269	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	328	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.03	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.98	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.05	%	1		
SiO2	28.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2810	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-17	Customer sample ID: ESS-5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	985	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4060	uS/cm	1		2/5/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	244	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/10/2020
Magnesium	89.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Potassium	23.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Silicon	12.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/10/2020
Sodium	589	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/10/2020
Strontium	4.36	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/10/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Barium	0.017	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/12/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Boron 11	0.476	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/12/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/12/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/12/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Lithium	0.183	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Silicon	13.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/12/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Strontium	4.14	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/12/2020
Uranium	0.0116	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Vanadium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/12/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	810	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.94	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	1.39	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	835	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	281	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	343	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	46.02	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.69	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.36	%	1		
SiO2	27.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2800	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-18	Customer sample ID: ESS-6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	975	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3280	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	185	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	82.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	434	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.43	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.022	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.373	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.161	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.011	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0061	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0089	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	634	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.68	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	662	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.44	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.36	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.51	%	1		
SiO2	23.3	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-19	Customer sample ID: SSS-1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	801	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3300	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	180	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	79.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	18.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	430	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.370	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.159	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	0.0050	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0125	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.56	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.58	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	0.51	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	660	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	279	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.33	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.68	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.32	%	1		
SiO2	22.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2170	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-20	Customer sample ID: SSS-2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	776	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	192	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	84.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	451	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.56	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.366	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.158	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0156	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	629	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.62	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	655	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	279	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.16	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.60	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.59	%	1		
SiO2	22.4	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2200	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-21	Customer sample ID: SSS-3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	826	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3290	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	188	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	82.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	442	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.368	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.164	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	0.0129	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0145	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.59	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	630	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.67	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	0.65	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	657	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.19	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.88	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.43	%	1		
SiO2	22.7	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-22	Customer sample ID: SSS-4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	809	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	188	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	82.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	19.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	445	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.51	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.363	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.160	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	0.0072	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0134	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.56	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.65	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	0.59	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	232	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	283	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.19	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.99	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.27	%	1		
SiO2	22.5	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-23	Customer sample ID: SSS-5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	808	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		2/11/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.1	ph Units	1		3/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	191	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	2/19/2020
Magnesium	84.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Potassium	19.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/19/2020
Sodium	445	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	2/19/2020
Strontium	3.52	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/19/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	2/20/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Boron 11	0.359	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	2/20/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	2/20/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	2/20/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Lithium	0.160	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Nickel	0.0085	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	2/20/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	2/20/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020
Zinc 66	0.0164	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	2/20/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.59	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Chloride	628	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020
Fluoride	1.63	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrate	0.58	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	2/25/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	2/25/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	2/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	231	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	282	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/2/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200112
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 1/30/2020 12:49:30 PM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project: San Solomon Springs
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.09	meq/L	1		
Cations total	36.30	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.28	%	1		
SiO2	21.8	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200112-24	Customer sample ID: SSS-6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	822	mg CaCO3/ L	1		